

Using Set Up Candid Clips as Viral Marketing via New Media

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Abstract—This research's objectives were to analyze the using of new media in the form of set up candid clip that affects the product and presenter, to study the effectiveness of using new media in the form of set up candid clip in order to increase the circulation and audience satisfaction and to use the earned information and knowledge to develop the communication for publicizing and advertising via new media. This research is qualitative research based on questionnaire from 50 random sampling representative samples and in-depth interview from experts in publicizing and advertising fields. The findings indicated the positive and negative effects to the brands' image and presenters' image of product named "Scotch 100" and "Snickers" that used set up candid clips via new media for publicizing and advertising in Thailand. It will be useful for fields of publicizing and advertising in the new media forms.

Keywords—Candid Clip, Effect, New Media, Social Network.

I. INTRODUCTION

MARKETING theory is a complex system of ideas concerning the best practices for publicizing a product. In preparation for a product launch, a business must choose whether to invest in traditional advertising such as print, outdoor and online advertising, or other forms of promotion including email and fliers. Purchasing media space on television and radio networks is another delivery method for promoting a launch. Other businesses choose to rely on viral marketing, creating interest in a product online and allowing social networks and individual customers to promote the product through conversation. [2] The main purposes of publicizing and advertising are to increase sales and profits, encourage trial and usage and remind advertising.

We all are surrounded by many media such as press, television, radio, cinema for more than 100 years. At the present, there're new media that is used via internet or social network and mobile devices such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Youtube, LINE and etc. Social media is a form of communication that accessible to all levels of people in short time which spreadout extensively around the world at the present under the whole time development of computer technology. Social media tends to be priority media for people in the future. [4]

Matrix of communication for persuasion is divided into independent variable which is communication and dependent variable which is attitude or behavior changing. [5] Communication via new media in the form of set up candid

clip is independent variable in this study.

Viral marketing is one of the important issues in this study. Viral marketing is popular for marketing communication via new media which this kind of marketing must reside social networks. [3] Viral marketing is an amazing method of generating traffic and leads but also creates a great demand for a yet to be released product. Viral marketing is not a marketing strategy. It's in genius and quite valuable for many marketers that rely on the internet for a full time income. Viral Marketing is so successful because it creates the curiosity and desire needed to generate the demand for a product or service. [1] Because of the trend of advertising nowadays that cheap budget and quick communication in wide range are on demand. Then, viral marketing is the way that makes the brand or product can do the publicizing and advertising in lower budget and reach the majority audience rapidly.

We've noticed the trend of viral marking that many of them combine with communication via new media. We've seen both positive and negative feedback from the audience of communication via new media especially in the form of set up candid clip.

As viral marketing, form of set up candid clips and new media are new things which are budget saving for publicizing and advertising and accessible anywhere and anytime. But the most significant issue that we have to intensively study is the result of using set up candid clips as viral marketing via new media or its effectiveness from the audience that the researchers have studied for further proper methods for using of viral marketing and new media effectiveness in the future.

II. PURPOSES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of this study were to analyze the using of new media in the form of set up candid clip that affects the product and presenter, to study the effectiveness of using new media in the form of set up candid clip in order to increase the circulation and audience satisfaction and to use the earned information and knowledge to develop the communication for publicizing and advertising via new media.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research was a qualitative research arising from content analysis from the set up candid clips that were used as new media for publicizing and advertising via social network of 2 products in Thailand which are **Scotch 100** Essence of Chicken (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tZ_vaoO2eCo&list=PLk68a1djsw1uLt-13FgotqMP5va9tFv9N&index=1) and

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SnickersChocolate(<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4v1haaj-ggU> and <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mz83sYATHbM&list=PLk68a1djswlU-Lt-13FgotqMP5va9tFv9N&index=3>), questionnaire, in-depth interview, documents, literature and relevant research work. At first in methodology plan, the researchers would like to ask for product circulation from Scotch 100 and Snickers before, during and after the set up candid clip were launched. But both companies denied giving the product circulation because it's confidential. Another research tool is questionnaire which used both close and open ended by spreading out random sampling questionnaire which was made from Google Docs (https://docs.google.com/forms/d/16r87beTEYcEK_n7PfQECQEos3ZaCIWiyIplvZjttO_Qk/viewform) to get 50 representative samples' answers via social network which were Facebook and LINE. A strength, weakness, opportunity and threat (SWOT) methodology was employed as an analysis tool for in-depth interview from 2 experts in advertising and publicizing fields which the questions are open ended.

IV. RESULT OF THE STUDY

In this research, there're 3 set up candid clips that were used as new media for publicizing and advertising via social network of 2 products in Thailand, Scotch 100 (1 clip) and Snickers (2 clips) were analyzed, the story of each set up candid clip are as following;

Scotch 100 Essence of Chicken (The presenter of this clip of Scotch 100 is a very famous actor in Thailand named AnandaEveringham. The situation was set in the advertising film production in studio around 4AM after the last scene of that advertising film shooting.) Assistant Director came to talk with Ananda and asked him to take 1 more shooting as special scene for this advertising film. He was asked to dance Gangnam Style (Korean famous music with the dancing style of the singer named Psy) Ananda was mad and screamed to everyone because the director said that the shooting was finished already. At that time, it's 4AM in the morning. They'd been worked too long time and he's not impressed about shooting another special scene for this advertising film that the assistant director asked him to do. He threw the water bottle and scolded to everyone that he's made fame for 10 years but how come the production team asked him to do stupid dance. Instantly, Ananda danced Gangnam Style and all the production team danced with him seriously and joyfully. Letters on screen "Give it 100% best shot in every life roles".

According to Youtube.com statistic [6], there're 734,033 views for this clip, which 8,560 people pressed "like" for this clip and 140 people pressed "unlike" for this clip (checked on 12 June, 2014)

Fig. 1 Views and likes information for set up candid clip of Scotch 100 Essence of Chicken in www.youtube.com [6]

Snickers Chocolate Clip No.1 (The presenter of this clip of Snickers is a moderate famous actress in Thailand named AomSuchaManaying. The situation was set in the mall that the presenter was working. She walked by to meet her fans.) AomSucha met her fans while she was working at that mall. AomSucha got mad and screamed to her fans after they screamed her name too loud and would like to take pictures with her. One of the fans ran to her with her name electronic display. AomSucha pushed her and the electronic display fell. All fans raised their voice shockedly.

According to Youtube.com statistic [7], there're 79,836 views for this clip, which 143 people pressed "like" for this clip and 90 people pressed "unlike" for this clip (checked on 12 June, 2014)

Fig. 2 Views and likes information for set up candid clip no.1 of Snickers Chocolate in www.youtube.com [7]

Snickers Chocolate Clip No.2 (The presenter of this clip is the same person as the 1st one named AomSuchaManaying. The situation was set in the dressing room in the mall that she walked in after having problem with her fans.) Letters on screen “Don’t let hungriness make you’re not yourself”. AomSucha complained about everything around her. One staff ran into the dressing room and asked what happen to her. AomSucha had Snickers in her hand and said sorry for getting mad because of hungriness. She’s fine now. Letter on screen “Don’t let hungriness change you. When you need snack, you need Snickers”.

According to Youtube.com statistic[8], there’re 319,609 views for this clip, which 893 people pressed “like” for this clip and 1,002 people pressed “unlike” for this clip (checked on 10 February, 2014).

Fig. 3 Views and likes information for set up candid clip no.2 of Snickers Chocolate in www.youtube.com [8]

There’re 50 representative samples who answered the 1st part of questionnaire about personal detail as following;

- For genders issue, there’re 25 of male and 25 of female.
- For ages issue, there’re 1 of age 11-15, 7 of age 16-20, 3 of age 21-25, 21 of age 26-30, 11 of age 31-35, 3 of 36-40 and 4 of age 40+.
- For education level issue, there’re 1 from elementary school level, 2 from secondary school level, 38 of bachelor degree level, 6 of master degree level and 1 of doctoral degree level.

The 2nd part of questionnaire were 10 close ended questions asking representative samples before watching 3 of set up candid clips those were used as viral marketing via new media of Scotch 100 and Snickers. The important results are as following;

Fig. 4 Result from 50 representative samples of “Like” and “Unlike” communication via new media in the form of set up candid clip

Fig. 5 Result from 50 representative samples between people who like set up candid clips of Scotch 100 and Snickers

For the effect of using set up candid clips as viral marketing via new media to the products, there’re 15 people (30%) will buy the product of Scotch 100 after watching the set up candid clips as viral marketing via new media of Scotch 100 and there’re 23 people (46%) will buy the product of Snickers after watching the set up candid clips as viral marketing via new media of Snickers. For the effect of using set up candid clips as viral marketing via new media to the presenters, there’re 44 people (88%) like and 37 people (74%) will keep on following the works of AnandaEveringham, the presenter of Scotch 100 and there’re 44 people (88%) like and 29 people (58%) will keep on following the works of AomSucha, the presenter of Snickers.

For the result of in-depth interview from 2 experts in advertising and publicizing fields, they have 6-8 year experience in advertising and publicizing and won many international advertising awards including Cannes 2012. They used to work on viral marketing project which used the new media for publicizing and advertising via social network but they haven’t worked in the form of set up candid clip. They think that people like communication via new media in the form of set up candid clip is because of the new and strange presentation form and the reason that people don’t like communication via new media in the form of set up candid clip is because people don’t like to get deceived. The strengths of communication via new media in the form of set up candid

clip are getting awareness overnight and get followed by the realistic set up. The weakness of communication via new media in the form of set up candid clips bad brand image in case of bad content. The opportunity of communication via new media in the form of set up candid clips in good direction if it's based on good content, not too violent form. The threats of communication via new media in the form of set up candid clip are the bad content which cause bad image to the brand and audience emotions including consumers' rejection which would not worth the investment for this kind of publicizing and advertising.

V. CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY

According to the findings from content analysis, result of questionnaire and in-depth interview, we can conclude that communication via new media in the form of set up candid clip is rather effective way of communication in quick awareness getting (talk of the town) but in short period of time (short-term trend). As the viral marketing plan, it's effective to be talk of the town in short time but most of the react from the audience were in negative way. Then, using set up candid clips as viral marketing via new media would be suitable for the product or brand that requires reminding to the product or brand by not concern about positive or negative feedback.

Communication via new media in the form of set up candid clip is effective about satisfaction to female more than male, in the age of 31-35 and 41+ more than the other ages and in the level of education of secondary education more than the other levels of education.

Both Scotch 100 and Snickers' set up candid clips were effective in awareness and satisfaction to the audience. But the effectiveness of satisfaction of Snickers' set up candid clip is less than Scotch 100's.

For the issue of effect to the products, both Scotch 100 and Snickers' using of set up candid clips as viral marketing via new media were not effective in circulation increase. On the contrary, they decreased the circulation of Scotch 100 and Snickers evaluated by result of questionnaire. Before watching the clips, there're 19 people (38%) used to buy Scotch 100's product and there're 33 people (66%) used to buy Snickers' product. After watching the clips, there're 15 people (30%) will buy Scotch 100's product (8% decreased from before watching result) and there're 23 people (46%) will buy Snickers' product (20% decreased from before watching result).

For the issue of effect to the presenters, using set up candid clips as viral marketing via new media decrease the popularity of the presenters. For the result of question before watching the clips, there're 44 people (88%) like Ananda, Scotch 100's presenter and there're 35 people (70%) like AomSucha, Snickers' presenter. For the result of question after watching the clips, there're 37 people (74%) will still follow Ananda, Scotch 100's presenter's work (14% decreased from before watching result) and there're 29 people (58%) will still follow AomSucha, Snickers' presenter's work (16% decreased from before watching result).

According to the analysis of open ended question about the reasons that representative samples like or don't like communication via new media in the form of set up candid clip, it can be divided into 3 groups which are positive reasons, negative reasons and neutral reasons or no comment. The interpretation from representative samples satisfaction to communication via new media in the form of set up candid clip, to the set up candid clips as viral marketing via new media of Scotch 100 and to the set up candid clips as viral marketing via new media of Snickers showed that using set up candid clips as viral marketing via new media is still rather effective in communicating with audience.

The conclusion from in-depth interview from 2 experts, we can conclude that the content is more important than the trend. Communication via new media should be based on good content in proper form. Because the set up candid clip in some issues are too sensitive to some target group audience. It can cause disappointment to the audience leading to bad image to the brand or product which will decrease the circulation and satisfaction from the customers. Communication via new media is a lot cheaper than other media but serious consideration of content and form is highly required.

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- [8] <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mz83sYATHbM&list=PLk68a1djsw1uLt-13FgotqMP5va9tFv9N&index=3>

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